

ANAGRAFICA PROGETTO

Spoke	7
ACRONIMO DEL PROGETTO	ZEPHIRO
Azienda Capofila	Caffini SpA
Data inizio progetto:	01/05/2024
Durata:	15 mesi
Data fine progetto:	31/07/2025

Partner	Denominazione	Dimensione di impresa	P.IVA/CF	CUP	Sede di Progetto
Capofila	Caffini SpA	MI	02945220230	B43D24000060004	Via Marconi 2, Palù, Vr

Deliverables 1.2 – Libreria nodo ROS2

```
import sys
import time

import can
import numpy as np
import rclpy
from fv_interfaces.msg import AgroInfo, VolumeSections
from rclpy.callback_groups import ReentrantCallbackGroup
from rclpy.executors import ExternalShutdownException, MultiThreadedExecutor
from rclpy.node import Node
from std_msgs.msg import Float64

class CAN_socket(Node):
    def __init__(self):
        super().__init__("can_socket_node")

        self.bus = can.interface.Bus(
            interface="socketcan", channel="can0", bitrate=250000
```

```
)
```

```
self.get_logger().info("CAN OK")
```

```
self.timer_send = self.create_timer(  
    timer_period_sec=0.1,  
    callback=self.timer_send_callback,  
    callback_group=ReentrantCallbackGroup(),  
)
```

```
self.sub_info = self.create_subscription(  
    VolumeSections, "/vra_vision/volume_sections", self.volume_callback, 1  
)
```

```
# self.pub_speed = self.create_publisher(Float64, "/gpio_speed", 1)  
# Speed  
# self.speed = 0.0
```

```
self.target_rate = 1500 * 100  
self.pwm_r = 4 * [0.0]  
self.pwm_l = 4 * [0.0]  
self.actual_rate = 1500 * 100
```

```
def volume_callback(self, msg):
```

```
    # self.target_rate = msg.info_data.target_rate * 100  
    self.pwm_l = [i * 100 for i in msg.left]  
    self.pwm_r = [i * 100 for i in msg.right]  
    self.pwm_r.reverse()
```

```
    # print((np.mean(self.pwm_l) + np.mean(self.pwm_r)) / 2 / 100**2)  
    self.actual_rate = self.target_rate * 0.75 + (self.target_rate * 0.25) * (  
        ((np.mean(self.pwm_l) + np.mean(self.pwm_r)) / 2) / 100**2  
)
```

```
    # print("T: ", self.actual_rate)
```

```
    # print(self.target_rate, self.pwm_r, self.pwm_l)
```

```

def byte_format(self, data, length):
    return int(data).to_bytes(length, "little")

# Send Target rate message
def timer_send_callback(self):
    f = self.byte_format
    # print(self.target_rate, f(self.target_rate, 8))
    #
    # print(b"".join([f(0, 1), f(self.pwm_r[0], 3), f(1, 1), f(self.pwm_r[1], 3)]))

self.bus.send(
    can.Message(
        timestamp=time.time(),
        arbitration_id=0x0CFF6050, # prio + pgn + source adress
        data=f(self.actual_rate * 100, 8),
        is_extended_id=True,
    )
)

# # Send Volume message
# # data = b''.join([format(0,1), format(0,3), format(1,1), format(2000,3)]) # 2000 = 20.00*100
# # format = lambda x,l : int(x).to_bytes(l,'little')
# #
self.bus.send(
    can.Message(
        timestamp=time.time(),
        arbitration_id=0x0CFF6150,
        data=b"".join(
            [f(0, 1), f(self.pwm_l[0], 3), f(1, 1), f(self.pwm_l[1], 3)]
        ),
        is_extended_id=True,
    )
)

self.bus.send(
    can.Message(
        timestamp=time.time(),
        arbitration_id=0x0CFF6150,
        data=b"".join(
            [f(2, 1), f(self.pwm_l[2], 3), f(3, 1), f(self.pwm_l[3], 3)]
        )
    )
)

```

```

    ),
    is_extended_id=True,
)
)

self.bus.send(
    can.Message(
        timestamp=time.time(),
        arbitration_id=0x0CFF6150,
        data=b"".join(
            [f(4, 1), f(self.pwm_r[0], 3), f(5, 1), f(self.pwm_r[1], 3)]
        ),
        is_extended_id=True,
    )
)

```

```

self.bus.send(
    can.Message(
        timestamp=time.time(),
        arbitration_id=0x0CFF6150,
        data=b"".join(
            [f(6, 1), f(self.pwm_r[2], 3), f(7, 1), f(self.pwm_r[3], 3)]
        ),
        is_extended_id=True,
    )
)

```

```

def main():
    print("Hi from fv_driver_can.")
    rclpy.init(args=None)
    can_node = CAN_socket()
    executor = MultiThreadedExecutor()
    try:
        rclpy.spin(can_node, executor=executor)
    except KeyboardInterrupt:
        pass
    except ExternalShutdownException:

```

```
sys.exit(1)
```

```
finally:
```

```
    can_node.bus.shutdown()
```

```
    can_node.destroy_node()
```

```
    rclpy.try_shutdown()
```

```
if __name__ == "__main__":
```

```
    main()
```